

N-Hydroxy-N, N'-Diphenylbenzamidine-A New Type of Analytical Reagent. Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron (III)

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A sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of iron (III) is reported using N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine. The reagent in acetone develops a red-purple colour between pH 4.5-11.0 having its wavelength of maximum absorption at 530 nm. The colour system conformed to Beer's law between the limits 1.6-10.0 ppm of the metal.

N-Hydroxy-N, N'-disubstitutedbenzamidines, a new class of organic compounds has been found to possess several valuable properties as analytical reagents. Studies carried out in these laboratories showed that these are excellent reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V)¹, the gravimetric determination of copper(II)² and nickel(II)³. The reagent(III) is prepared by the reaction of N-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride, I with N-phenylhydroxylamine, II in absolute ether medium.

It may be seen that hydroxylamine itself gives the amidoxime (Ph-C(=NOH)-NHPh) which is tautomeric with the N-hydroxybenzamidine (Ph-C(=NPh)-NHOH). Using N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine as the reagent, a sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of iron(III) is reported. The reagent in acetone yields a red-purple colour between pH 4.5-11.0, the wavelength of maximum absorption being 530 nm. The colour system conformed to Beer's law between the limits 1.6-10.0 ppm of the metal. The sensitivity of the reaction as defined by Sandell is 0.018 μg of iron(III) per cm². The colour is stable for at least 30 hours. The molar absorptivity of the colour reaction calculated on the basis of iron is 3350 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Job's method of continuous variation has been employed to establish the metal to ligand ratio of the chelate in solution and it is concluded that iron(III) forms a 1:3 chelate with the reagent. The apparent stability constant of the complex calculated from Job's curves is 5.01 × 10⁻¹⁸.

Barium, strontium, calcium, aluminium, magnesium, tartrate, oxalate, fluoride, sulphate and chloride do not interfere with the determination. Many common metals seriously interfere.

Experimental

Synthesis of Reagent. Condensation of N-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride with N-phenylhydroxylamine in absolute ether medium furnished N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine. In the present investigation the imidoyl chloride has been synthesized following the procedure of Wallach⁴; phosphorus pentachloride being replaced by thionyl chloride. In actual practice, pure benzanilide was heated in an oil bath at 130°-150° with 20% molar excess of thionyl chloride for 90 minutes. The oily pale yellow N-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride was separated by distillation (175/12mm), yield, 75%.

12.0 g of N-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride (0.055 mole) were taken in about 150 ml of absolute ether in a 500 ml short necked round bottomed flask. To this N-phenylhydroxylamine, 6.1 g (0.056 mole) in absolute ether was added in portions over a 20 min period while stirring with a glass rod. A light brown oil slowly separated out. Stirring and shaking were continued till the light brown oil solidified and separated as shining crystals resembling sodium chloride. This was filtered off and washed with 3 × 20 ml portions of ether. The resulting N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine hydrochloride weighed 6.5 g.

The hydrochloride salt thus obtained was treated with 25 ml of N ammonia solution in a conical flask and the precipitated N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine free base was filtered off, recrystallized from petroleum ether (60°-80°): benzene (1:2) to give pale yellow crystals, yield, 4.5 g, m. p. 163°. (Found :

C, 79.06; H, 5.62; N, 9.87 per cent, calcd. for $C_{19}H_{16}N_2O$: C, 79.16; H, 5.55; N, 9.72 per cent. The substance was insoluble in water but soluble in chloroform, ethyl alcohol, acetone, benzene and acetic acid.

Reagent Solution. A 0.1% W/V (0.003 M approximately) solution of the reagent in acetone was used for the colour development. The reagent solution is stable for several days.

Standard Iron(III) Solution. 1.0 g Pure iron wire was dissolved in 50 ml of 1:3 nitric acid. It was boiled to expel oxides of nitrogen and diluted to one litre. Aliquots of this solution were diluted to desired concentrations.

Apparatus. Carl Zeiss(Jena) universal spectrophotometer VSU 1 was employed for absorbance measurements. The pH(Systronic pH metre Type 322) was adjusted with acetic acid and ammonia.

Recommended Procedure. An aliquot (5 ml) of iron(III) solution containing approximately 100 μg of the metal was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask and to this 3 ml of the reagent solution followed by 5 drops of 5N ammonia were added. The solution immediately turned red-purple. This was diluted to mark with acetone and the absorbance was measured at 530 nm. The absorbance spectra of the reagent and the iron complex are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of :
 A. The reagent in acetone, 0.1 per cent.
 B. Fe (III)-Reagent purple complex at pH 6.3 ; Fe (III), 110 μg /25 ml, reagent, 3 ml (0.1 per cent), solvent acetone.

Results and Discussion

The colour developed instantaneously and the complex was stable for at least 30 hr. Effect of variation of pH on the complex formation was studied. The optimum pH range was found to be 4.5 to 11.0. To achieve the maximum colour development a 1 to 3 molar ratio of the metal to reagent should be employed. In practice for every 0.1 mg of the metal 3 mg of the reagent are added. This concentration represents a 6 fold molar excess of reagent.

Lambert-Beer Law. Varying concentrations of iron(III) were taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask and the colour was developed and measured using the recommended procedure. Beer's law was obeyed over the range 40 μg to 250 μg of iron in a 25 ml solution.

Effect of Foreign Ions. The influence of diverse ions on the absorbance was studied. There is generally no interference by the following ions. Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , F^- , oxalate and tartrate. Several common ions including Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} interfered with the determination.

Composition and Stability Constant of Complex. Advantage is being taken of the red-purple chelate formed when iron reacts with the reagent to determine the nature and metal-ligand stability constant of the complex. A reaction ratio of iron-to-reagent of 1-3 is shown by the method of continuous variation and mole ratio method. The stability constant of the chelate has been determined spectrophotometrically using Job's method with non-equimolar solutions and the value is 5.01×10^{-18} .

References

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